

Effect of Rural Health Programmes on Women's Livelihood in Ogun State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Access to healthcare is very important to people's wellbeing and development, especially among women in rural communities where health disparities remain stark. This study examined how rural health programmes affect women's livelihoods. Data were collected using an interview schedule from 120 women who were selected with the simple random sampling technique. Data were analyzed with frequency count, percentage, mean, and Pearson product moment correlation. Findings showed that the mean age of the women was 39 years, with an average of 5 persons in their household. More than half (60%) of the women had secondary education, and 72.5% earned between ₦50,000 and ₦100,000 monthly. Most were traders (48.3%) and farmers (40%). Health services accessed include family planning and immunization. Many (55.8%) of the women had a favorable perception that the health programmes influence their livelihoods and well-beings. The challenges included limited health services ($\bar{x}=1.98$), fear of side effects ($\bar{x}=1.93$), and prevalent cultural or religious beliefs ($\bar{x}=1.83$). A significant relationship ($r = 0.423$, $p < 0.005$) exists between access to health services and the perceived effect of health programmes on women's livelihood activities. The study concludes that rural health programmes are crucial in improving women's livelihoods. It recommends that in order to promote economic resilience in rural areas, the government should equip and expand rural health centers, the agriculture and health ministries should work with local women to address cultural misconceptions, and health services should be integrated.

Key words: Health programmes, Women's livelihood, Healthcare access, Cultural beliefs and Perception

INTRODUCTION

Rural health care services are vital to the health and well-being of individuals in agrarian areas. Health service access is essential, as it has a direct impact on rural women's health, autonomy, income, and economic participation (Cornish et al., 2021). Despite the federal government's goal of achieving congestion-free and affordable health services with the introduction of NHIS in 1999, the rural-urban gap continues in Nigeria due not only to long travel distances from homes, poverty level, state of amenities, sociocultural attitude, and low level of health information (Ezeudu and Fadeyi 2024). Though the government and development partners have instituted rural health programs, these services continue to be utilized inequitably in most rural communities owing mainly to poverty, distance-based access, limited awareness, social-cultural norms, and weak health system infrastructures. Lack of access to healthcare imposes health burdens and risks on rural women, thereby reducing their ability to make decisions and engage actively in income-generating activities (Haley and Marsh 2021).

Women are also central players in the agricultural value chain. The role of women in the processing

and marketing of agricultural products is inevitable to mention; they are evidently one of the major actors in value addition and farm waste conversion. Women are definitely involved in these activities, which go a long way in post-harvest losses and also in having a sustainable environment. The participation of women in farming is high and exceeds that of men (Table 5). In sub-Saharan African countries, including Nigeria, high levels of women are engaged in farming: about 73% are women farmers involved in cash crops and food crops, crop cultivation, arable and vegetable gardening; 16% are in postharvest operations; and 15% are in agroforestry (FAO and ECOWAS 2018; FAO 2019).

Recent empowerment and intervention for women has assisted in boosting their presence even in agricultural production. The health of women could influence their activities and engagements. Empirical evidence shows that access to reproductive health services positively impacts women's education, labor force participation, and overall empowerment (Olamijuwon & Odimegwu, 2021). Therefore, it is important to investigate the relationship between rural health programmes utilization and the economic and social well-being of rural women. This will help

to determine health programmes access transforms into measurable improvements in women's livelihoods in Ogun State. In order to address this issue, the study examines effect of rural health programmes on women's livelihoods in Ogun State, Nigeria. It specifically; describes the socio-economic characteristics of rural women; identify available rural health programmes; their accessibility, and challenges faced by women in accessing the health services and the perceived effect on their livelihoods. The hypothesis also the study stated that there is no significant relationship between accessibility and the perceived effects of rural health programmes on women's livelihoods.

METHODOLOGY

Study area

This study was conducted in Ogun State, located in the southwestern region of Nigeria. Ogun State shares boundaries with Lagos State to the south, Oyo and Osun States to the north, Ondo State to the east, and the Republic of Benin to the west. It spans an area of approximately 16,762 square kilometers and has a population exceeding 5 million people (National Bureau of Statistics, 2021). Ogun State lies between latitudes $77^{\circ}01'$ and 7070° , as well as longitudes $2^{\circ}n2^{\circ}45'$ and $3^{\circ}55'$. The study area is within the rainforest zone, with the freshwater swamp and mangrove in the southeast of the state. The two peaks of annual rainfall in the early and late periods of the year support agricultural activities. Abeokuta, which is the capital of the state, is more urbanized, but most of the state comprises rural and semi-urban communities with poor infrastructure and social amenities. The state has 20 Local Government Areas (LGAs). The predominant ethnic group is Yoruba, while other tribes such as Hausa, Igbo, and Igede can be seen in many parts of the state. Women are represented in the agriculture space in Ogun State, and so are other members of their households. Rural health centers and clinics can be seen in some of the communities, but they are underserved in terms of healthcare and facilities. This makes the selected location relevant for the study because of the condition of the health care services; certain interventions were given to support the rural people's health for better living.

Sampling procedures and data collection

The population of this study consists of rural women whose livelihoods are within the agrarian communities. A multi-stage sampling was used to select the sample size for this study. This is described: at the first stage, fifty percent of the four agricultural zones in Ogun State were selected using simple random sampling techniques. Stage two

involves the selection of two (2) blocks with simple random sampling to make a total of four (4) blocks; 3 cells were selected from the four blocks to make 12 cells. At stage three, from each of the selected cells, which consist of villages, one village was selected with simple random sampling from each cell to make a total of 12 villages. Lastly, a simple random sampling technique was used to select ten women, making a total of 120 women from rural households. The primary data was collected through the use of an interview schedule. The instrument collects information on socioeconomic characteristics, health programmes, livelihood activities, and the perceived impact of healthcare on livelihoods.

Measurement of Variables

Livelihood activities were measured at the nominal level as Yes = 2 and No = 1. Accessibility was measured using a Likert scale and categorical responses: highly accessible (healthcare programmes are available and can be used at all times) = 3, moderately accessible (healthcare is accessible but can only be used occasionally) = 2, and not accessible (healthcare is available but cannot be used at all) = 1. The perceived effect of the healthcare programmes on livelihood was measured with a scale based on five-point responses of Strongly Agree = 5, Agree = 4, Undecided = 3, Disagree = 2, and Strongly Disagree = 1. Challenges in accessing rural health services are categorized as Major Challenge =3, Minor Challenge=2, or No Challenge=1.

Data analysis

Data obtained were subjected to descriptive analysis such as frequency count and percentage distribution and presented in tables and charts. The PPMC analysis was used to test the hypothesis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic characteristics of respondents

Entries in Table 1 reveal that the average age of the women was 39 years; this implies that the women are predominantly in their productive age. Many (65.8%) of them are within the age bracket of 31-50 years. This concentration in middle age shows that the women are still active and in child bearing age, faming and engaging in income generating activities thereby requires reproductive health services (Agbenyo et al., 2023). The findings also show that 55 percent of them women were married, while 26.7% were either separated, divorced, or widowed, indicating different level of social support and mental care which requires healthcare decisions.

The educational attainment of the women reveals that 60 percent of them had secondary education, followed by 24.2 percent with tertiary education, showing a moderately literate population. The average household size was 5 persons; this aligns with the national trends in rural households (NPC 2019). Most (72.5%) of them earned an average of ₦65,800 per month, which implies that many of the women with little income had poor access to healthcare services. Women’s low income persists in limiting their access to health services, especially in

rural and underserved areas where out-of-pocket expenses are onerous (Ogu et al., 2024). Saxena et al. (2023) asserted that low income restricts access to healthcare services, hence impeding healthcare utilization among women in rural communities. Over half of the women were Christian and Yoruba. Olutade-Babatunde et al. (2024) opined that sociocultural patterns are essential to health behavior and patterns of adopting health interventions, especially in the area of reproductive care.

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Age (years)			
Less than 31	26	21.7	39.00
31-50	79	65.8	
Above 50	15	12.5	
Marital Status			
Single	22	18.3	
Married	66	55	
Widowed	2	1.7	
Separated	16	13.3	
Divorced	14	11.7	
Education Level			
No formal education	10	8.3	
Primary	9	7.5	
Secondary	72	60.0	
Tertiary	29	24.2	
Household Size (persons)			
Less than 4 persons	46	38.3	5persons
4- 6 persons	70	58.4	
Above 6 persons	4	3.3	
Income per month (₦)			
<50000	30	24.9	₦65,800
50000-100000	87	72.5	
>100000	3	2.4	
Religion			
Christianity	74	61.7	
Islamic	28	23.3	
Traditional	18	15.0	
Ethnicity			
Yoruba	74	61.7	
Igbo	30	25.0	
Hausa	16	13.3	

Livelihood activities of the women aside from farming

The rural women sampled for the study were into farming activities, which are the common livelihoods in the study area. Antriyandarti et al. (2024) opined that female rural farmer frequently manage complex households while pursuing multiple income streams, including in the areas of agriculture and food security. Results presented in Figure 1 show other livelihood activities aside from farming that the women engaged in; these include trading (48.3%), processing (40%) and civil service (11.7%). The

implication is that women engaged in other income-generating activities such as buying, selling, and processing to support their income. Women farmers diversify livelihoods by engaging in off-farm activities like petty trading as a supporting alternative income activity (Mohammed and Favretto 2025). Palacios-Lopez (2017) asserted that women engage in multiple tasks such as processing food and marketing, including animal husbandry. Even women farmers that obtain higher educational qualifications seek formal job opportunities within the rural setting as a channel of income inflow for their households.

Figure 1: Other livelihoods apart from farming in the study area

Rural health programmes and services for women in the study area

Results in Table 2 show the healthcare services available in the study area that are known to women. More than eighty percent of women identified the National Family Planning Programmes (NFPP) and safe delivery and antenatal care as health care services they are familiar with in the study area. This is because women at bearing age require more medical attention to support them during pregnancy and nurturing of children and other members of their households. Curry et al. (2023) opined that quality improvement in health areas is not only about safe delivery but also about protecting their livelihood and improving the quality of antenatal care, which assists in uncomplicated deliveries. Awareness of free contraceptive healthcare services and HIV prevention healthcare programmes was relatively high, with more than 60 percent of women indicating the services are available for them in their utilization. Mukherjee (2021) asserted that the recent increasing knowledge of contraception methods among young

women strengthens community health for better living and livelihood improvements.

However, the Expanded Immunization Programmes for children and other family members was pointed out by 55 percent of women, and Prevention of Mother-to-Child Transmission of HIV (PMTCT) was also indicated by 51.7 percent. The rural women's health and well-being are very important for the survival of the households, not only for their domestic activities but also for livelihood improvement. Any deterioration of their health or that of their family member will distract them from domestic roles as well as their income-generating activities. Therefore, immunization of the women and other family members makes them strong and well protected against certain diseases and ailments that could make them sick. Access to healthcare reduces the burden of physical and mental health conditions. It assists in the prevention and management of disease conditions and reduces secondary complications associated with various diseases such

as communicable and non-communicable diseases

(Moroz et al., 2020; George et al., 2020).

Table 2: Rural healthcare services and programmes identified by women

Healthcare services and programmes	Frequency	Percentages
National Family Planning Programmes (NFPP)	98	81.7
Safe delivery and antenatal cares	98	81.7
Free contraceptives healthcare services	78	65.0
HIV awareness and prevention healthcare programmes	72	60.0
Government Immunization Services for Children	68	56.7
Expanded Programmes on immunization (EPI)	66	55.0
Prevention of Mother-to-Child Transmission of HIV (PMTCT)	62	51.7
Family planning services by NGO	60	50.0
Health outreach programmes/ mobile clinics for reproductive services	52	43.3

Accessibility to rural health programmes by women in the study area

Despite considerable awareness about rural healthcare services and programmes by the women, the accessibility of these programmes remains uneven. The result of the mean score reveals that on average none of the rural health programmes have high accessibility. The implication is that most of the rural health programmes, if not all, are not adequately accessed, and it influences the well-being and health status of the rural women. In rural health situations, unfairness exists in the delivery of health facilities, with rural areas getting fewer healthcare services compared to urban settings. A large portion of the remote region has poor access to health services (WHO 2017). Although fifty percent of the women indicated that the health workers assistance for immunization healthcare was highly accessible, 70% rated medical advisory and consultation as moderately accessible. However, vaccine availability scored low and was not accessible, with only 28.3% reporting consistent vaccine access. Geographic challenges, such as long travel distances (mean =

1.93) and location of the health facilities (mean = 1.70), were significant, particularly for immunization access in the rural communities.

The accessibility of reproductive health services showed moderate concern (mean = 1.72), consistent with previous findings by Udenigwe et al. (2022), who opined that community elders attributed the non-use of maternal health services to poor quality of care. The concept of poor quality of healthcare included inadequacy of professional healthcare personnel and abusive manners of healthcare providers. A critical concern was the low frequency with which health workers disseminated information about family planning methods (mean = 2.07), indicating a need for ongoing community-based education to ensure proper reorientation. In addition, poor communication not only makes access to essential health services difficult to obtain but also feeds myths about maternal health, these gaps, focused on educational initiatives that encourage community involvement and confidence in healthcare systems.

Table 3: Accessibility to rural health programmes and services by women

Accessibility	Highly Accessible	Moderately Accessible	Not Accessible	Mean
Location of immunization centers in your community.	50(41.7)	56(46.7)	14(11.7)	1.70
Health and medical advisory and consultation services	24(20.0)	84(70.0)	12(10.0)	1.90
Available vaccines and drugs for treatments	34(28.3)	22(18.3)	64(53.3)	1.90
Family planning and reproductive health services	52(43.3)	44(36.7)	24(20.0)	1.77
Free contraceptives reproductive healthcare	56(46.7)	42(35.0)	22(18.3)	1.72
Health outreach and mobile healthcare services.	20(16.7)	32(26.7)	68(56.7)	1.90
Assistance of health workers for immunizations	60(50.0)	46(38.3)	14(11.7)	1.62
Distances to health facilities make services accessible	34(28.3)	60(50.0)	26(21.7)	1.93
Easy to get immunization for your child and mother	44(36.7)	58(48.3)	18(15.0)	1.78
Information on family planning methods	22(18.3)	30(25.0)	68(56.7)	2.07

Rural women's perception on the effect of healthcare accessibility on livelihoods

Figure 2 shows rural women overall perception of how their access to healthcare services affects their health and well-being status and its implication on their livelihoods. Many (65%) of the rural women perceived that the impact of the health access on their livelihoods is unfavorable. The implication is that their access to healthcare service is poor and thereby has a negative impact on their livelihoods because once their health deteriorates; their ability to engage efficiently in their livelihoods becomes difficult. Sewell and Desai (2016) asserted that poor access to education and healthcare contributes to the inability to strengthen human capabilities and improve livelihoods. Entries in Table 4 show a mean score of 4.18, agreeing at family planning services enabled individuals to plan and manage their families and finances properly. Many (81.6%) agreed that immunization programs saved families from child mortality and its trauma. This implies that access too immunization which is one of the health services, relieve rural households from financial stress and the burden of spending on diseases and ailments that can hinder their health and well-being. Habib et al.2021) opined that weak health systems and poor access to health services hinder women’s ability to generate income and secure livelihoods; access to modern contraception not only supports reproductive autonomy but also strengthens economic stability. The result further accentuates the concrete benefits of public health interventions in reducing diseases and sudden death as well as strengthening economic resilience. Kalu et al. (2025) opined that immunization coverage improves child and mother health in rural communities.

Furthermore, over 700 percent of the rural women believed that health programs had improved maternal and child health in their communities. Achieving reproductive health programs was also seen as beneficial, with 70% of participants acknowledging improvements in their personal health and well-being, reflected in a mean of 3.93. A mean score of 3.92 indicates that the rural women valued health counseling services for increasing their knowledge about health issues. Notwithstanding, the results also reveal that cultural beliefs (mean = 3.77), family planning methods (mean = 3.22), and misinformation were prevalent; 31.7% strongly agreed and another 25% agreed that side effects of healthcare services offered to them can affect their well-being and engagement in livelihoods. Moreover, 75% of rural women agreed or strongly agreed that some community members believe family planning can result in infertility (mean = 3.82), and 70 percent of them indicated that cultural and religious misunderstandings surrounding family planning (mean = 3.68) prevent rural women from utilizing the healthcare services even when they are required to sustain their health in their income-generating activities. This also hinders the provision of healthcare services by the health workers. Over 60 percent of the rural women agreed that reproductive health services are valuable, but the length of waiting times or delays are not bearable and occasionally violate women's privacy, and 51.7 percent felt discriminated against or judged when seeking care. Wehabe et al. (2024) identified similar difficulties and advocated for more patient-centered care training. and stressed the importance of continuous professional development for the health workers on how to attend to women in the rural setting.

Figure 2: categorization of rural women perception on effect of healthcare on livelihoods

Table 4 Perceived effect of healthcare access on livelihoods by rural women

Perceptual statement	SA%	A %	U%	D%	SD%	Mean
Family planning services have enables me to better plan my family and finances	36.7	50.0	10.0	1.7	1.7	4.18
Access to immunization has helped reduce child mortality in my household	38.3	43.3	15.0	1.7	1.7	4.15
Reproductive health programs have improved my health and well-being	30.0	40.0	23.3	6.7	0.0	3.93
These health programs have made it easier for me to engage in economic activities	16.7	35.0	33.3	11.7	3.3	3.5
Family planning services are sometimes culturally or religiously misunderstood	25.0	45.0	8.3	16.7	5.0	3.68
Some family planning methods have caused me discomfort or health issues	21.7	21.7	18.3	33.3	5.0	3.22
Immunization services are not regularly available in my area	16.7	26.7	20.0	33.3	3.3	3.2
My community lacks proper awareness about the benefits of these programs	13.3	40.0	10.0	15.0	21.7	3.24
The health workers sometimes lack the resources or skills to provide proper care	25.0	25.0	33.3	11.7	5.0	3.08
Access to health programs has improved maternal and child health	46.7	25.0	16.7	6.7	5.0	3.77
Some people in the community believe family planning leads to infertility	46.7	45.0	8.3	10.0	6.7	4.02
There is fear and misinformation about the side effects of immunization	20.0	25.0	31.7	8.3	3.3	3.82
The health counseling services have increased my knowledge about health issues	31.7	46.7	15.0	3.3	6.7	3.73
These programs contributed to fewer school absences for my children due to illness	30.0	25.0	31.7	5.0	8.3	3.58
Reproductive health services have empowered me to make better health decisions	36.7	30.0	33.3	1.7	3.3	3.9
Reproductive health services are not always respectful of women’s privacy	20.0	45.0	21.7	8.3	5.0	3.67
Immunization programs have reduced the cost of treating preventable diseases	45.0	38.3	13.3	3.3	1.7	4.18
I experience long waiting times or delays when accessing these services	20.0	46.7	21.7	10.0	1.7	3.73
I sometimes feel judged or discriminated against when seeking reproductive health	1.7	20.0	15.0	26.7	6.7	3.43

NB: SA =Strongly Agree, A=Agree, U=Undecided, D= Disagree, SA=Strongly Disagree

Challenges in accessing healthcare programs by rural women

The findings reveal that challenges that hinder access to healthcare services are multifaceted. The most prominent challenge is high transportation cost, acknowledged as a major challenge by 61.7 percent of rural women, with a mean score of 1.42. Closely following is financial constraint, which 53.3 percent indicated as a major challenge. These financial barriers imply that finance is important to access healthcare services and that even when services are available, without money there will be a limitation to utilization. Language barriers (mean = 1.68) and insufficient health information (mean = 1.78) were also identified as significant challenges, with more than half of respondents citing them as major challenges. Likewise, spousal or family disapproval was indicated as a major barrier by 46.7% of rural women, with a mean of 1.72, which shows that the influence of family and gender factors is involved in health decision-making.

Golestani, Farahani, and Peters (2025) asserted that young women in rural and agrarian communities faced a number of challenges in accessing healthcare services, such as a lack of knowledge, unfavorable

attitudes, gender insensitivity, psychological discomfort, and financial affordability. A mean score of 1.83 indicates that cultural or religious views continue to have a significant impact, with 30% of them indicating it as a serious issue. Gomes et al. (2021) opined that rural populations opt to maintain cultural practices focused on their health and use herbal medicines and mystics related to religious beliefs in self-care practices. Hesitancy or avoidance is also influenced by health providers' negative attitudes (mean = 1.72) and fear of side effects (mean = 1.93), which were mentioned as key concerns by 30% and 40% of respondents, respectively. Cultural appreciation and respect for diversity are important to be recognized so that the unique characteristics of this country can be kept (Rückert, Cunha, & Modena, 2018). Another critical challenge is the limited availability of health services (mean = 1.98), with only 35 percent indicating it as a major issue. This can be seen in the disparities in health service delivery across the rural communities. Even when the healthcare service is available, professional healthcare providers are not adequate (mean = 1.72). This indicates access difficulties to healthcare services to meet demand.

Table 5: Challenges faced in accessing healthcare services

Challenges	Major Challenge	Minor Challenge	No Challenge	Mean
Cultural or religious beliefs	36(30.0)	68(56.7)	16(13.3)	1.83
High cost of transportation to health facilities	74(61.7)	42(35.0)	4(3.3)	1.42
Insufficient information about health services	60(50.0)	26(21.7)	34(28.3)	1.78
Spousal or family disapproval	56(46.7)	42(35.0)	22(18.3)	1.72
Inadequate professional healthcare providers	52(43.3)	50(41.7)	18(15.0)	1.72
Language barriers	60(50.0)	38(31.7)	22(18.3)	1.68
Financial constraints	64(53.3)	42(35.0)	14(11.7)	1.58
Poor attitude of health workers	48(40.0)	58(48.3)	14(11.7)	1.72
Limited availability of health services	42(35.0)	38(31.7)	40(33.3)	1.98
Fear of side effects	36(30.0)	56(46.7)	28(23.3)	1.93

Result of hypothesis

The result of the hypothesis presented in Table 6 reveals that there is a positive relationship between women's access to healthcare and their perception of how well-being and health status influence livelihood activities. The result is statistically significant at a p-value less than 5%; it implies that deterioration of women's health will definitely have a negative impact

on their livelihoods. The perception of women on their health status and livelihoods is that it is related to the kind of access they have to healthcare services. The result indicated that as the access to health services increases for the rural women, so also do their livelihoods. The more access the rural women have to health programs and services, the better their health condition and the more women engage in income-generating activities.

Table 6: Result of correlation between healthcare and perceived effect on livelihoods

Variables	r	p-value	decision
access to healthcare and its perceived effect on livelihoods	0.423	0.003	significant

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study concluded that the rural women in the study area were young and still actively seeking access to healthcare services. This interfered with women’s socio-economic status and their livelihoods. Although rural women are aware of these, actual access and utilization remain constrained. Socio-cultural beliefs, religion, fear of side effects, poor attitude of health workers, language barriers, and limited health services, among others, were the challenges identified. The rural women's healthcare access was found to significantly influence livelihood engagement. It is positively correlated with the perceived impact of health programmes on their livelihoods and well-being. Despite the benefits reported, such as reduced child mortality, improved

financial planning, and enhanced maternal well-being, persistent challenges continue to impede optimal access and utilization. It is thereby recommended that there is a need to strengthen community-based health education and awareness campaigns that dispel myths and promote informed health-seeking behavior by the Ministry of Health. The health infrastructure and workforce capacity must be improved through intentional investment in facilities, personnel, and consistent medical supply chains by the government. The rural primary health workers and extension agents should endeavor to localize their health content and deliveries in indigenous languages for better understanding of the rural women.

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